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STRUCTURAL INSIGHTS ON THE RECOGNITION MODE OF ANTIBODIES TARGETING GLYCANS

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Over 100 antibody-based therapeutics have received approval for treating various severe human diseases, significantly improving the lives of patient [1]. Antibodies are primarily employed in combating cancer, autoimmune conditions, and persistent inflammatory diseases [1]. While the majority of these antibodies are in the IgG format, there are several emerging alternatives, including antibody-drug conjugates (ADCs) and diverse antibody fragments, such as nanobodies, domain antibodies, and bispecific antibodies (BsAbs) [1].

Anti-glycan monoclonal antibodies are valuable in both healthcare and research, finding applications in cancer and infectious disease treatments and disease diagnostics. However, the limited availability of high-quality anti-glycan monoclonal antibodies underscores the demand for innovative technologies in their discovery. For instance, characterizing antibodies has posed a significant challenge due to their inherent flexibility, making their production and purification as recombinant proteins a complex process. In our laboratory, we have developed a robust pipeline for analyzing the Fab portion of anti-glycan antibodies. We will now outline our comprehensive approach to the production and characterization of antibodies, commencing with sequence generation, followed by protein production and purification, culminating in the characterization process. The multidisciplinary antibody-glycan binding characterization involves computational design, NMR-based chemical studies, biophysical techniques (Isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) and biolayer interferometry (BLI)) and structural analysis via X-Ray Crystallography. These techniques collectively offer precise insights into the paratopes, enabling us to modify them further to enhance their binding parameters.

Within this framework, our team has effectively analyzed the Fab portion of diverse antibodies, specifically those that target tumour associated glycans (TACA), such as L2A5 [2], and a Diheteroglycan (DHG), a well-characterized capsular polysaccharide decorating *Enterococcus faecalis* cell wall (DHG01) [3].

References:

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